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Empirical Assessment of Nigeria Debt Burden (1981-2020)

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Abstract

The paper assesses the Nigeria debt burden using Generalised Linear Model in relation to colonialism and imperialism. Time series data were considered. The presence of Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (ARCH) effect in the data property induced the use of Generalised Linear Model (GLM) in its methodology. For every 0.97 unit increase in External Debt (EXDT), Gross Domestic Product (GDP) increased by 1 unit. EXDT was significant at 5% with probability value of 0.0228. For every 4.7 unit increase in Total Debt Servicing (TDS), GDP increased by 1 unit. However, the probability of 0.4022 showed that it was insignificant; which implies that the real burden of Nigeria debt can be linked to external debt burden. It is seen as re-conquest of Africa through imperialism. The paper recommended a multi-year rescheduling rather than year by year basis as a short term viable policy option. In the long run, export promotion and import substitution strategy can be adopted as a viable macroeconomics policy options.

Keywords: GLM, ARCH, debt burden, GDP

Introduction

African nations have broken away from the shackles of colonisation but financial neocolonialism a stronger force than political colonisation still persists. Nwoaha (2017) posits that no economy in the world, no matter how develop, is self-sufficient. However throwing caution to the wind in terms of public borrowing may not be ideal for developing countries. Jozsef and Mahua (2012) analysed colonialism in terms of practice and worldview. As practiced, he opined that it involves the colonisation and determination of a society by settlers from a different society. The worldview perception sees colonialism as a global geopolitical, economic and cultural principle that is rooted in the worldwide expansion of West European capitalism. While colonialism is the total subjugation of an assumed superior race over an acclaimed inferior one, imperialism refers to monetary dominance of these assumed superior clients. Imperialism and colonialism are two sides of a coin. While colonialism takes physical control, imperialism takes monetary control. As at 1986, Nigeria total debt stood at 42.2 billion naira. Obasanjo became president in 1999 and work out a partial write-off through his finance minister to the tune of 19 billion dollars, leaving Nigeria with somewhat clean slate as at when he finished his leadership in 2007 (Chita, 2019). Chita further noted that Nigeria has borrowed more in the last three years than it did in the 30 years; taking debt level as at 2019 from #12 trillion to #25 trillion without visible impact. Oladeinde (2021) cited the World Bank report that listed Nigeria among countries with the highest debt risk exposure across the world. The International Development Association (IDA), a World Bank financial institution that offers concessional loans and grants to the poorest developing countries cited in Oladeinde (2021) reported that, with the current debt exposure, Nigeria ranked fifth among the top 10 countries with highest debt risk exposure. The top four countries are India, Bangladesh, Pakistan and Vietnam.

Currently, the data which includes the total external and domestic debts of the federal government of Nigeria, thirty-six state governments and the federal capital territory, shows that Nigeria's public debt was \$92.626 billion at the end of third quarter of 2021. By Implication, Nigeria spend a sum of \$520.78 million on external debt servicing in the third quarter of 2021, rising by 74.2% compared to \$298.9 million recorded in the preceding quarter (Q2, 2021). Geoff (2021) observed the debt market as a dragnet all around. The writing submitted that whether one borrows from the domestic market or the drying international market, there are sufficient risks that could suffocate the already bleeding economy to death and mortgage the future of the country. Burkina Faso leader Thomas Sankara has once associated

debt to slavery. He made this submission three decades ago at the Organisation of African Unity (now the Africa Union). The speech unequivocally concluded that debt was a threat to the economic survival of African countries (Geoff, 2021). Geoff further observed that Nigeria total debt profile stood at #32.9 trillion. While the federal government's share of the debt is #26.9 trillion, comprising #10.9 trillion external and #16 trillion domestic, the 36 states and Federal Capital Territory owes approximately #6 trillion, which is about five times their total 2020 internally-generated revenue (IGR).

Njuguna et al., (2021) paper submitted that sustainability can be achieved when debt is used to fuel capital accumulation and income convergence to bridge the domestic saving gap as suggested by Harrod and Domar model. There must be constant quest for knowledge through research to decipher the 'good' and the 'bad' of debt in a country economic development process. The international dependency revolution theory has within its ambit three theories of concern which include: the neo colonial dependency model, the false- paradigm model and the dualistic development thesis. The false paradigm model queried the model put forward by economic development experts. It submitted that experts often prescribed sophisticated concepts, elegant theoretical structures and complex econometric models of development that often leads to inappropriate or incorrect policies. Do we categorise Harrod and Domar model as a false paradigm model? Doing so means one is hast in decision. Harrod and Domar did not advocate for debt in financing the domestic saving gap. They only advocated for capital accumulation to grow the GNP of a country. The path to tread in accumulating this capital to increase or sustain the GNP towards the path of economic growth is a choice of individual economic agent. This research is precipitated on the above assertion. All hands must be on deck to find solution to this rising and unabated Nigeria debt profile. In line with the above, the major objective of this paper is to assess the Nigeria's debt burden with a view of determining its impact on Nigerian economy, using Generalised Linear model.

Conceptual and Theoretical Literature

Debt is a financial obligation which represents a liability. When a government borrows, the debt incurred is a public debt. National debt is all claims against the government held by the private sector of the economy or by foreigners whether interest bearing or not (and including bank held debt and government currency, if any), less any claims held by the government against the private sector and foreigners (Modigliani, 1961 cited in Anyanwu, 1993). National debts include the currency, short term debt, floating and funded debt and internal and external debt. From the point of view of the borrower, according to Anyanwu, external debt has three component parts namely: public debts, publicly-guaranteed debts and private non-guaranteed debts; while from the point of view of the creditors, it could be official creditors or private creditors. It could also be gross or net, marketable or non- marketable, short term, medium term or long term, interest bearing or non-interest bearing, government used securities or special issues and project loan or jumbo loan.

A debt burden is a financial obligation owe by a country which is difficult to repay (Anyanwu, 1993). Public debts burden refers to the hardship resulting from acquisition of debts. Theoretically, three main burdens are recognised: the burden of the principal, the burden of interest payment and the burden of future generations. This writing is anchor on three theories: the crowding-out, Harrod and Domar and the two gap theories. Crowding out theory postulate that rising public spending reduces private investment. It measures the relationship among deficits, private investment and the rate of interest. Continuous deficit financing through external debt leads to higher interest rate which in turn reduces business investment. Both Harrod and Domar are interested in discovering the rate of income growth necessary for a smooth and uninterrupted working of the economy (Jhingan, 2010). In order to grow, economy must save and invest a certain proportion of their Gross National Product. However, there is shortage of funds to invest in capital project in developing countries which necessitate the need for external financing through borrowing. The two gap model proposes that there is shortage of savings to finance domestic investment and shortage of foreign exchange to finance imports of capital or intermediate goods. The domestic savings gap and the foreign exchange gap sometimes necessitate the need for borrowing.

Empirical Literature

Nwoaha et al (2017) used error correction model to analyse the effect of total external debt on the Nigeria economy. Two variables were captured in the model: Gross Domestic Product and total external debt. The results of the work showed that external debt exert negative and significant influence on GDP. As more external loan is obtained, GDP plunged and shrink. The research did not completely eradicate the viability of external loan to increase GDP but insist that external debt should be channeled towards productive investments that will not only increase the GDP, but also pay the capital and interest of such deficit financing. Obiamaka (2019) explored the effect of external debt burden on

economic growth in Nigeria. Three variables were used in the model. These include: GDP, money supply and external debt. The result shows that external debt has a negative effect on economic growth. This study is in line with (Nwoaha et al, 2017). Both studies observe negative effect of external debt on economic growth. Obiamaka study recommended alternative sources of government revenue rather than dependent on foreign financing. However the study demands thorough analysis. The external debt variable was insignificant in relation to economic growth. Except viable economic explanation is given in regard to the insignificant of external debt variable in the model, accepting the recommendation and using it for policy prescription may be misleading. Furthermore, the study advocated for government to source for loan internally (domestic borrowing). The study excluded total debt outstanding in its model. Studies such as: Kingsley et al (2021), Geoff (2021) and Ojukwu (2021) have shown that external debt and internal debt are two edged sword, if not properly managed, it can be inimical to an economy.

Kingsley (2021) gives empirical evidence to debt overhang theory. The study posits that national debt becomes a burden when debt overhang is rising, foreign reserves are inadequate to cover short term external debt and government revenue is inadequate for debt servicing. The paper used three variables to measure debt burden. These include: debt overhang, which can also be measured by debt-to-GDP ratio. Debt overhang also depicts a debt burden so large that an entity cannot take on additional debt to finance future projects. Other variables used are: short term external debt-to-reserves ratio (reserves adequacy) and debt service cost-to-government revenue ratio (revenue adequacy). The paper used exchange rate as a control variable while economic stability is measured with real GDP growth rate. Auto Regressive Distributed Lag Model (ARDL) was used in its methodology. The results show that the regressors cause a diminishing impact on the economic stability in the long run. However, in the short run, all the variables except debt overhang have a negative and significant impact on economic stability. Kingsley (2021) work may suffer from methodological issue. The paper reported that the variables used in the model are stationary both at levels and at first difference. Theoretically, unit root test is a pre test that forces researchers, with intention of using Ordinary Least Square (OLS), to establish the stationarity of the data set. If stationarity is established, OLS will give an optimal econometric estimate compared to ARDL. However, the theoretical underpinning of the use of debt overhang (total debt to GDP ratio), debt-to-foreign reserves ratio and debt service-to- government revenue ratio as a parameter to measure a country debt burden is a step in the right direction.

Onaolapo and Kayode (2015) analysed the impact of external debt management on economic growth. The study found out that external debt management had positive impact on economic growth. The paper advocated for increase in Nigeria's export base, restrictions in public spending and increase in non-oil exports. Babayemi and Olorunpomi (2017) used Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) in analysing the effect of debt burden on Nigeria's economic growth. External debt was used as independent variable while GDP was used as dependent variable. The study revealed that for every one percent increase in external debt, GDP shrink by twenty-nine percent. The paper submitted that the negative consequences of excessive external debt lead to debt overhang and crowding out effect on investment. The study associated debt burden to poverty; insisting that countries with high debt burden can fall into poverty trap with its attendance low level of investment, low export diversification accompanying low economic growth. Projects that generate substantial revenue to pay for capital and interest on any debt incurred were advocated for by Babayemi and Olorunpomi (2017).

The micro aspect of family debt was analysed by Xiao and Yao (2021). The paper looked at the implication of debt burden on family structure. The findings revealed that married families with children seem to have more debt. The findings also suggested that married family with children seems to be late in debt payment. How consistent is United Nation Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) of 2030 and accumulation of unsustainable debt profile by African countries? Ojukwu (2021) provides a viable answer to the above question. Ojukwu laid emphasis on SDG two, of zero hunger and SDG three of good health and well-being. In the methodology, Spearman rank correlation was used in the study of external debt and SDG, with empirical evidence from Nigeria. The paper argued that debt accumulation should lead to increase in infrastructure with its attendance decrease in poverty index. The study observes that this is not the case from the results obtained from the analysis. The paper warned that debt overhang should be avoided and that policy should be put in place by the debt management agency to gradually liquidate Nigeria rising external debt.

Methodology

The paper uses time series data for Nigerian economy for the period 1981 – 2020. The data was obtained from the World Bank data base. GDP is the dependent variable while EXTND and TDS are the independent variables. Having observed the ARCH effect, the paper uses GLM for the parameter estimate. The ARCH and GARCH(1,1) model is specified as $Y_t = X_t \lambda + U_t$; where $\sigma_t^2 = a + \alpha a_{t-1}^2 + \beta \sigma_{t-1}^2$. 'Y' is the dependent variable, 'X' is the independent

variable and 'U' is the error term. The mean equation is written as a function of exogenous variables with an error term. Where σ_i^2 is the one period forecast variance. The variance is the conditional variance. The conditional variance ($\sigma_i^2 = a + \alpha a_{t-1}^2 + \beta \sigma_{t-1}^2$) is a function of three terms. A constant term 'a' the ARCH term (a_{t-1}^2) and the GARCH term (σ_{t-1}^2). The functional form of the GLM is given as: $GDP^* = \phi + \phi_1 EXT D^* + \phi_2 TDS^* + U_i$; Where GDP is the gross domestic product, EXT D is external debt, TDS is total debt servicing and the starred variables are the transformed variables that satisfy the standard least-square assumptions.

Results and Discussion

Unit root test is a pre-test. It forces analysts to test for the stationarity of the data before application of OLS or other econometric techniques. The result in table 1 shows that EXT D is I(1). This is arrived at when the test critical value of -2.938987 is compared with the Augmented Dickey- Fuller (ADF) statistics value of 0.467589. Similarly, TDS is also I(1). When the critical value of GDP is compared with the ADF statistics, it shows that GDP is I(0). In line with economic theory, GDP, TDS and EXT D are all first difference stationary.

Table 1: Unit Root Test

Variables		ADF Test Stat.	conclusion		ADF Test Stat.	conclusion
EXT D	Level	0.467589(-2.938987)	I(1)	1st Diff.	-4.787555(-2.941145)	I(0)
GDP	Level	5.551660(-2.960411)	I(0)	1st Diff.	3.308712(-2.967767}	I(0)
TDS	Level	1.331379(-2.938987)	I(1)	1st Diff.	-5.469583(-2.941145)	I(0)

Table 2: ARCH/GARCH model output

Dependent Variable: GDP

Method: ML ARCH - Normal distribution

GARCH = C(3) + C(4)*RESID(-1)^2 + C(5)*GARCH(-1)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.58E+17	8.40E+16	1.886851	0.0592
GARCH(-1)	0.523838	0.163569	3.202557	0.0014

Result extracted from E-views 9 output

Table 3: Generalized Linear Model

Dependent Variable: GDP

Method: Generalized Linear Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
TDS	4.967284	5.992801	0.828875	0.4072
EXT D	0.973247	0.427600	2.276068	0.0228

Result extracted from E-views 9 output

In advanced econometric research, the econometric tools to employ depend on the characteristics depicted by the data set. It is a normal practice to inspect the data properties before the application of econometric techniques. In this study, the data properties shows that the sum of the ARCH and GARCH coefficient in table 2, i.e GARCH (-1) with the value 0.523838 is close to one indicating a unitary property that required application of GLM in the relationship between the regressors and the regressand. Table 3 shows that for every 0.97 unit increase in external debt GDP increase by 1 unit. The probability value of '0.0228' shows that EXT D is significant. The implication of the above result shows that as external debt increases GDP also increased. TDS is used to measure the total debt burden in the economy. For every 4.97 unit increase in TDS, GDP increased by one unit. However the probability value of 0.4072 shows that it is insignificant. The implication of this is that the real burden of Nigeria debt can be linked to external debt burden.

Conclusion

The paper recommended the classical rule of external debt, that is, debt should be incurred on productive self-liquidating investment. The economic viability, financial desirability and technical feasibility of the project to be financed with external debt must be properly appraised. A multi-year rescheduling should be considered rather than year by year basis as a short term viable policy option. In the long run, export promotion and import substitution strategy can be adopted as a viable macroeconomics policy options. Nigeria, as nation, should resist the re-conquest bids of the developed nations. Burkina Faso leader Thomas Sankara once said 'debt origins come from colonialism's origins. Those who lend us money are those who had colonised us before. Under its current form, that is imperialism-controlled, debt is a cleverly managed re-conquest of Africa, aiming at subjugating its growth and development through foreign rule. Thus, each one of us becomes the financial slave, which is the real true slave'.

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4 The Impact of Digital Innovation Drivers on Administrative Efficiency in Edo State Tertiary Institutions

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Abstract

Innovation culture brings about an open atmosphere within a firm in which employees, as an innovation engine, are motivated to show more creativity and hence provide the firm with more opportunities for innovation. Management competency relates to management's readiness to deploy innovations, which translates into superior organisational outcomes. The application of innovative drivers has been identified as the potential factor contributing to the challenges experienced in the job performance of administrative staff in tertiary institutions in Edo State. It is, therefore, imperative to address all these challenges in the light of providing a system and structure that provides the process from ideas to successful implementation of the needs it addresses and the services it delivers. Krejcie and Morgan formula was used to arrive at a sample size of 217. Structured questionnaire and interview guide were adopted, validated and used for data collection. Cronbach's Alpha coefficients for the constructs ranged from 0.90 to 0.97. The response rate was 100%. Data were analysed using descriptive and inferential (Pearson Product Moment Correlation

and regression) statistics. Findings revealed that innovation drivers have strong positive and statistically significant relationship with the job performance of administrative staff of tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria ($R = 0.669$, $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that Innovation drivers influence administrative staff performance in order to achieve the institutions' set out objectives.

Key Words: innovation driver, administrative efficiency and management.

Introduction

Innovation is a principal instrument by which organisations adapt to the constantly changing demands of the contemporary evolving environment (Alemayehu & Woldemariam 2020). Innovation is a process through which essential ideas are translated into new methods to add worth for the organisation, employees and other stakeholders. It is without doubt that the problem of most organisations today is ensuring a constant route to establish an organisation where innovation is necessary to continue its existence, making innovation a significant factor for different establishments to thrive in this innovative era. In a broader term, innovation can be seen as the process by which organisations, through their products or services, undergo vital and constant transformational changes leading to the gradual adjustment in activities cumulatively resulting in substantial operational process (Rajabi, Boles, Alejandro, & Sarin 2021). In a nutshell, innovation comes in through converting new ideas into products, processes or services and putting them into use through various deliveries (Bellini, Dell'Era, Frattini, & Verganti 2017). Scholars have since then proposed different meanings and measurements of innovation drivers, some of which even overlapped with other established constructs such as environmental pressure, technological capability, knowledge exchange and boundary spanning. There are common characteristics that were noteworthy for defining innovation drivers. First, innovation driver indicates "certain circumstantial forces that stimulate organisations to innovate". Secondly, innovation drivers relate to the technical factors enabling organisations to develop innovative products and processes. Another study describes innovation drivers as a relative arrangement that facilitates the sharing of knowledge and Information needed to innovate in and between organisations, as well as initiatives to co-innovate across the boundaries of departments, organisations and partnerships (Adenekan, 2019).

Innovation drivers are those elements that make innovation work in organisations. According (Poutanen, Soliman, & Stahle 2016), intangible elements like culture, personal schemes, resistance to change, politics, and fears are normally underestimated in innovation management systems in comparison to more tangible elements such as the resource infrastructure and the information systems that support the innovation process itself. Innovation drivers are a complex undertaking that originates from many sources, necessitates the involvement of various stakeholders, could manifest itself in several forms and ways, and might receive different conceptualisations and practical applications (Laureiro-Martínez, & Brusoni, 2018). The instrument of innovation drivers can be measured as (innovation culture, management competency, and organisational learning), adapted from literature and found applicability and relevance with the resource-based view theory (Luyombya, & Ndagire 2020). Innovation culture brings about an open atmosphere within a firm in which employees, as an innovation engine, are motivated to show more creativity and hence provide the firm with more opportunities for innovation. Management competency relates to management's readiness to deploy innovations, which translates into superior organisational outcomes. Organisational learning is a dynamic process for knowledge creation, acquisition and integration, facilitating innovation performance (Byrne, 2010).

In most tertiary institutions in Nigeria, with greater emphasis on tertiary institutions in Edo State, introducing disruptive innovative drives into the administrative management sector has destabilised the working equilibrium by providing new service processes and altering standard working structures and dynamics. Despite the tertiary institution being essentially an adopter rather than a developer of innovations, administrative staff in these institutions are currently trying to adapt and adapt to the paradigmatic shift in how administrative processes are conducted, and organisational models are framed to achieve higher value-added across the engagement process. These challenges may have culminated due to the late adoption of innovative drives in the tertiary education system. Both internal factors, associated with an organisation's dynamic, innovative capabilities, and external drivers, related to orientation, and availability of technological advancements, are inducing these tertiary institutions to implement innovative management approaches and practices. When organisations fail to provide speedy, innovative drives appropriately, the employee's job performance is more likely to suffer.

Literature Review

When it comes to customers, competitors, and technical developments, knowledge and data collecting, interpretation, and dissemination play crucial roles in the innovation process (Chen, Wang & Huang, 2020). According to (Saunila, 2020) new ideas emerge when individuals in an organisation communicate and build upon their existing bodies of knowledge. Technical, market, and design knowledge are just a few examples of the types of multidimensional complementary knowledge needed for innovation (Saunila, 2020). More than anything else, an organization's ability to learn and apply new information is what drives innovation. A company's ability to maximise its resources and remain competitive is enhanced by a well-designed learning system. Businesses who invest heavily in learning initiatives will have greater success than their rivals in the area of innovation. In addition to increasing an organization's adaptability in terms of product development and market penetration, purposeful and continuous learning also facilitates the constant dissemination of knowledge among firm employees (Dimitrova, Fernandes, Malik, Suryani, Musso, & Wiium, 2021). Learning not only helps businesses develop new goods more quickly and effectively, but it also helps them successfully bring those items to market.

One of the most important factors in determining the long-term success of a business or industry is how innovative its management is. Nonetheless, many businesses don't adopt it. Companies need to figure out how to successfully innovate because it is crucial to their growth and survival. Both internal and external influences have been shown to affect an organization's capacity for innovation. A study, for instance, identified four categories of elements that influence innovation: innovation characteristics; societal; organisational; and individual. They argued that innovation success is affected by learning orientation as a subset of organisational characteristics. Additionally, several academics agree that learning is an essential business skill and a primary source of innovation inside companies (Aboobaker, & Ka, 2023). Moreover, studies have shown that businesses that encourage employees to keep learning do better than their competitors. Successful product development and effective process modifications are only possible when businesses have the organisational capability of learning.

Organisational learning is a dynamic process that helps boost innovation performance (IP) by generating new knowledge, acquiring new knowledge, and integrating that knowledge (Hernández-Perlines, Ariza-Montes, Han & Law 2019). Some studies have looked into the factors that affect organisational learning in order to encourage innovation and found that an organization's innovation culture (IC) plays a crucial impact. Using the framework of contingency theory, Innovation culture creates an environment within an organisation where people are encouraged to express their creativity and help the business seize new chances for innovation. Prior research into the impact of organisational learning on innovation success often failed to adequately account for other contextual elements.

In light of the calls for research into the effects of innovation culture on success, the current study set out to determine how innovation culture moderates the link between organisational learning and innovation performance. Companies need to constantly develop their products, services, and business strategies if they want to continue growing in the future. However, only a select few businesses have proven they can consistently introduce market-altering breakthroughs. Further complicating the already difficult task of innovation management is the rapid pace at which globalisation, greater rivalry, the acceleration of technical transition (particularly digitization), and other environmental variables are changing (Al Aina & Atan 2020).

Different innovation concepts and methodologies enhance the complexity of innovation management, despite the fact that innovation is essential for maintaining a competitive edge and future growth. The idea of agility is being introduced to innovation management as a means of overcoming these challenges and responding to environmental uncertainty (Hanifah, Abdul Halim, Ahmad & Vafaei-Zadeh, 2019). An examination of strategic management revealed the sectors where agility has prompted significant advances. Introduced to SD for the first time, agile approaches are meant to enhance the final product by making the process more resilient to the effects of change and uncertainty.

Several sectors, including customer integration, quality, and forward thinking, have shown success using these techniques. A company's future success may also be aided by its agility if it can rapidly introduce new goods, services, and business models. The application of agility in the innovation process is relatively unexplored, despite the fact that both innovation and agility are seen as essential for a company's performance in today's uncertain circumstances. Key facilitators not previously highlighted in the literature were identified through a literature survey. Second, qualitative expert interviews are used to reflect on and supplement these derived enablers with regards to their attributes and impact on the beginning of the innovation process. To this purpose, we create a novel framework called the Agile Front purpose of Innovation (AFEI) to show businesses how they can boost their innovation efforts by emphasising agility. The dynamic capability approach is related to the management of innovation since it promotes the necessity

for a company to continually update its resources. Using a wide range of disciplines, researchers were able to agree on a definition of innovation as "a multi-stage process where organisations transform ideas into new/improved products, services, or processes" (Rehman & Iqbal, 2020).

The two approaches to innovation management, research and development (R&D) management, and innovation management, which encompass all activities from the research stage through the market introduction stage, can be grouped into several stages. The model presented by the authors provides a comprehensive look at how new products are developed. Often referred to as the "front end of innovation," the early phases of the process are crucial to the overall success of the innovation. There are a number of different ways to define the pioneering phase of innovation. The front end of innovation is the first part of the innovation process, and it consists of the steps done to develop an idea before it is presented to others (Singh, 2020).

Before diving into a formal innovation process, there is the "front end" of innovation. Opportunity identification, analysis, and ideation are all part of the front end of innovation, but so are concept selection and business case creation, according to this definition. The concept of combining the early phases of innovation, including ideation, idea selection, and business case development (Zeb, Akbar, Hussain, Safi & Rabnawaz 2021). This expanded definition shows that innovation is not confined to a single creative process but rather encompasses its entirety. A framework of the triggers and essential parts of innovation management was developed based on the front end of the innovation model, which included market pull and technology push considerations (Hurley & Hult, 1998). Several external elements affect the model's three primary triggers: market demand, business interest, and technological capability.

Theoretical Framework

Theory of Information Life Cycle Management

Similar to the birth, growth, and eventual demise of a biological creature, the Information Life Cycle Model views information as something that is created, kept, and used for as long as it has value, and then either destroyed or archived. The characteristics of the information life cycle model suggest that it is most suited for use by businesses that manage paper records. Researchers have shown that the life cycle model is not applicable to the study or management of electronic information within an organisation. Information continuum theory emerged in response to what its proponents saw as flaws in the information life cycle hypothesis. In the 1980s and 1990s, Australian archival theorist Frank Upward expanded on and popularised the Canadian-born information continuum theory (Malliouris, 2021).

A key tenet of the continuum theory is that there is no sharp break between the many stages of information, from its inception to its final disposal. To ensure the accuracy, validity, and completeness of information, the information continuum model unites office administrators and archivists under a unified data storage structure (Kurbonov & Saidov, 2022). The information life cycle idea is compared with a view from the information continuum. Information storage, according to the life cycle theory, can be roughly divided into two categories: active and historical. On the other hand, the information continuum has given administrators and archivists a framework for considering how to better integrate information-keeping and archiving procedures. According to the hypothesis of the "information life cycle," data goes through a series of transformations before "dying," while some data are "reborn" as archives (Kurbonov & Saidov, 2022).

Computers, video, audio tape, and film are only a few examples of the current technical technologies that have made information management easier and more effective. These gadgets can store vast amounts of data and have eliminated the bottlenecks that slowed down data storage in the past, making it possible to create, process, organise, and retrieve information at the speed of light. Despite these advances, paper record storage is still widely employed across the board, including at Edo State's higher education institutions. Since it describes the steps records take from creation to disposal, this theory lends credence to and is pertinent to the independent variable, record management practises.

Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of this study comprises of four hundred and eighty-one (481) administrative staff of University of Benin, (Federal), Benson Idahosa University, (Private) Igbinedion University, (Private) Edo State College of Education, Igueben, (State) Auchu Polytechnic, Auchu (Federal) and Ambrose Alli University (State). The sample size of this study is two hundred and seventeen (217) which were selected randomly from all administrative staff of the six institutions. This sample size was gotten from Krejcie and Morgan (1970)3 sample size). The instrument was a structured questionnaire adapted from previous empirical studies.

To validate this study, instrument items were gathered through related literature review and adaptation from questionnaires that have been used by other researchers. The researcher subjected the questionnaire to a reliability test to check the internal consistency of all items measuring each variable in the study. The reliability of the instrument was done through a pilot study using twenty-five (25) copies of the questionnaires which were administered to the administrative staff of Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA) which is not part of the study. A primary data was collected to address the objectives of the study through a structured questionnaire in line with existing literatures. The researcher analysed the data collected using the descriptive and inferential statistic for the items in various sections of the questionnaires. The data collected for the study was analysed using Ordinary Least Square regression technique using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 25.

Results and Discussion of Findings

A total of two hundred and ten (217) copies of questionnaire were administered, and two hundred and three (203) copies were returned. After sorting the questionnaires one hundred and eighty-seven (194) copies were certified as duly filled and considered usable. The useable questionnaire represented 89.4% response rate. Based on the decision scale, the overall mean for innovation drivers is 3.39, which shows that respondents agree with the statement depicting innovation drivers as being in the middle of the range. This indicates that administrative personnel at tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria, have a relatively high level of innovation drivers, and that there are opportunities for management to continue providing an enabling environment that enables for obtaining a higher level of innovation drivers.

Demographic Information of Administrative Staff of Tertiary Institutions in Edo State, Nigeria

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	108	55.7%
	Female	86	44.3%
Age	30 years and below	37	19.1%
	31-40 years	64	33.0%
	41-50years	76	39.2%
	51years and above	17	8.8%
Educational qualifications	SSCE	21	10.8%
	HND/BS.c	68	35.1%
	M.Sc	92	47.4%
	Ph.D	13	6.7%
Work experience	10 years and below	60	30.9%
	11-24 years	95	49.0%
	25 years and above	39	20.1%

Source: Field Survey Results 2023

This section consists of background and respondent's information that describes basic characteristics such as gender of the respondent, age of the respondent and faculty. This table shows the demographic and personal profile of respondents used for this study. Demographic and personal profile of respondents as shows profile of gender indicated

that 108 respondents representing 55.7% were male while 86 respondents representing 44.3% were females, indicating that most of the respondents were male. Demographic and personal profile of respondents as shows the age revealed that 37 respondents representing 19.1% were between ages 30years and below, 64 respondents representing 33.0% were between 31-40 years, 76 respondents representing 39.2% were between 41-50 years, 17 respondents representing 8.8% were between 51years and below, indicating that there were more respondents within the age 41-50 years. Furthermore, 21 respondents representing 10.8% indicated that they had SSCE, 68 respondents representing 35.1% had HND/B.Sc, 92 respondents representing 47.4% had M.Sc, and 13 respondents representing 6.7% had Ph.D. Also, 60 respondents representing 30.9% indicated to have worked for 10 years and below, 95 respondents representing 49.0% have worked between 11-24years and 39 respondents representing 20.1% have worked between 25 year and above.

Descriptive analysis of the Innovation Culture of Administrative Staff of Tertiary Institutions in Edo State, Nigeria

Innovation Culture:	SA	A	D	SD	Mean
My institution sends administrative staff on training to acquire new knowledge	(72) 37.1%	(102) 52.6%	(20) 10.3%	(0) 0.00%	3.27
Encourage administrative staff to use new methods of completing task given	(69) 35.6%	(116) 59.8%	(9) 4.6%	(0) 0.00%	3.31
Evaluate existing administrative policies for area to improve	(93) 47.9%	(90) 46.4%	(11) 5.7%	(0) 0.00%	3.42
At individual level I am constantly seeking new ideas to enhance my administrative capacity	(91) 46.9%	(94) 48.5%	(9) 4.6%	(0) 0.00%	3.42
My colleagues are open to new knowledge	(84) 43.3%	(85) 43.8%	(25) 12.9%	(0) 0.00%	3.30
My Colleagues are constantly seeking new information to get better at work	(119) 61.3%	(72) 37.1%	(3) 1.5%	(0) 0.00%	3.60
I find learning a critical aspect that enhance innovation	(94) 48.5%	(92) 47.4%	(8) 4.1%	(0) 0.00%	3.44
Average mean for innovation culture					3.394
Management competency	SA	A	D	SD	
Management use effective leadership style and are careful with how administrative staff issues are handled	(72) 37.1%	(115) 59.3%	(7) 3.6%	(0) 0.00%	3.34
There is evidence of interpersonal communication that aid work understanding for administrative staff	(70) 36.1%	(111) 57.2%	(13) 6.7%	(0) 0.00%	3.29
Our institution's management have the capacity to motivate administrative staff	(82) 42.5%	(101) 52.3%	(10) 5.2%	(0) 0.00%	3.37
We have management with proven integrity	(80) 41.2%	(108) 55.7%	(6) 3.1%	(0) 0.00%	3.38
We have management who can solve problem without creating chaos	(85) 43.8%	(99) 51.0%	(10) 5.2%	(0) 0.00%	3.39
We have management team who are actively involved in planning for the future	(92) 47.4%	(93) 47.9%	(9) 4.6%	(0) 0.00%	3.43
We have management team who are advocates of innovative behavior	(84) 43.3%	(101) 52.1%	(9) 4.6%	(0) 0.00%	3.39
Our institution has good working conditions which have enabled it to attract the right talent	(91) 46.9%	(96) 49.5%	(7) 3.6%	(0) 0.00%	3.43

Average mean for management competency						3.378
Organisational Learning	SA	A	D	SD		
Acquire new technologies/knowledge from various channels	(90) 46.4%	(95) 49.0%	(9) 4.6%	(0) 0.00%		3.42
Permits new knowledge, even when it conflicts with well-accepted experience and knowledge	(79) 40.7%	(106) 54.6%	(9) 4.6%	(0) 0.00%		3.36
Provides a favourable context for changing obsolete beliefs	(89) 46.1%	(96) 49.7%	(8) 4.1%	(0) 0.00%		3.42
Ready to change the way it operates	(101) 52.1%	(86) 44.3%	(7) 3.6%	(0) 0.00%		3.48
Establishing new values based on institutional needs	(92) 47.4%	(12) 6.2%	(1) 0.5%	(0) 0.00%		3.39
Abandon outdated beliefs/routines	(92) 47.4%	(86) 44.3%	(16) 8.2%	(0) 0.00%		3.39
Training on new work procedures	(74) 38.1%	(104) 53.6%	(16) 8.2%	(0) 0.00%		3.30
Average mean						3.37
Grand mean for Innovation drivers						3.39

Decision rule 1.00 – 1.49= strongly disagree, 1.50 – 2.49= disagree, 2.50 – 3.49 = agree, 3.50-4.00= strongly agree.

Source: Field Survey Results 2023

According to the results, 37.1% of the respondents strongly agree that my institution sends administrative staff on training to acquire new knowledge, 52.6% agree and 10.3% disagree. On average, the respondents indicated that my institution sends administrative staff on training to acquire new knowledge is high with a mean of 3.27. The result also showed that 35.6% of the respondents strongly agree that encourage administrative staff to use new methods of completing task given, 59.8% agree and 4.6% disagree. On average, the respondents indicated that encourage administrative staff to use new methods of completing task given is high with a mean of 3.31. The results also showed that 47.9% of the respondents strongly agree that evaluate existing administrative policies for area to improve, 46.4% agree and 5.7% disagree. On average, the respondents indicated that evaluate existing administrative policies for area to improve is high with a mean of 3.42. Results also showed that 46.9% of the respondents strongly agree that at individual level I am constantly seeking new ideas to enhance my administrative capacity, 48.5% agree and 4.65% disagree. On average, the respondents indicated that that at individual level I am constantly seeking new ideas to enhance my administrative capacity is high with a mean of 3.42. The results also showed that 43.3% of the respondents strongly agree that my colleagues are open to new knowledge, 43.8% agree and 12.9% disagree. On the average, the respondents indicated that my colleagues are to new knowledge is high mean of 3.30. Results also showed that 61.3% of the respondents strongly agree that my colleagues are constantly seeking new information to get better at work, 37.1% agree and 1.5% disagreed. On the average, the respondents indicated that my colleagues are constantly seeking new information to get better at work is high mean 3.60. Results also showed that 48.5% of the respondents strongly agree that I find learning a critical aspect that enhance innovation, 47.4% agree and 4.1% disagree. On average, the respondents indicated that I find learning a critical aspect that enhance innovation is high with a mean of 3.44 and innovation culture has a grand mean of 3.394.

According to the result, 37.1% of the respondents strongly agree that management use effective leadership style and are careful with how administrative staff issues are handled, 59.3% agree and 3.6% disagree. On the average, the respondents indicated that management use effective leadership style and are careful with how administrative staff issues are handled is high with a mean of 3.34. Results showed that 36.1% of the respondents strongly agree that there is evidence of interpersonal communication that aid work understanding for administrative staff, 57.2% agree and 6.7% disagree. On the average, the respondents indicated that there is evidence of interpersonal communication that aid work understanding for administrative staff is high with a mean of 3.29. Results also showed that 42.5% of the respondents strongly agree that our institution's management have the capacity to motivate administrative staff, 52.3% agree and 5.2% disagree. On the average, the respondents indicated that our institution's management has the capacity to motivate administrative staff with a high mean of 3.37. Results also showed that 41.2% of the respondents strongly

agree that we have management with proven integrity, 55.7% agree and 3.1% disagree. On the average, the respondents indicated that we have management with proven integrity is high with a mean of 3.38. Results also showed that 43.8% of the respondents strongly agree that we have management who can solve problem without creating chaos, 51.0% agree and 5.2% disagree. On the average, the respondents indicated that we have management who can solve problem without creating chaos is high with a mean of 3.39. Results also showed that 47.4% of the respondents strongly agree that we have management team who are actively involved in planning for the future, 47.9% agree and 4.6 disagree. On the average, the respondents indicated that we have management team who are actively involved in planning for the future is high with a mean of 3.43. The results also showed that 43.3% of the respondents strongly agree that we have management team who are advocates of innovative behavior, 52.1% agree and 4.6% disagree. On the average, the respondents indicated that we have management team who are advocates of innovative behavior is high with a mean of 3.39. Results also showed that 46.9% of the respondents strongly agree that our institution has good working conditions which have enabled it to attract the right talent, 49.5% agree and 3.6% disagree. On the average, the respondents indicated that our institution has good working conditions which have enabled it to attract the right talent are high with a mean of 3.43 and the management competency has a grand mean of 3.378.

The results showed, 46.4% of the respondents strongly agree that acquire new technologies/knowledge from various channels, 49.0% agree and 4.6% disagree. On the average, the respondents indicated that acquire new technologies/knowledge from various channels is high with a mean of 3.42. Results showed that 40.7% of the respondents strongly agree that permits new knowledge, even when it conflicts with well accepted experience and knowledge, 54.65 agree and 4.6% disagree. On the average, the respondents indicated that permits new knowledge, even when it conflicts with well accepted experience and knowledge is high with a mean of 3.36. Results also showed that 46.1% of the respondents strongly agree that provides a favorable context for changing obsolete beliefs, 49.7% agree and 4.15 disagree. On the average, the respondents indicated that provides a favorable context for changing obsolete beliefs is high with a mean of 3.42.

Furthermore, results also showed that 52.1% of the respondents strongly agree that ready to change the way it operates, 44.3% agree and 3.6% disagree. On the average, the respondents indicated that ready to change the way it operates is high with a mean of 3.48. Results also showed that 47.4% of the respondents strongly agree that establishing new values based on institutional needs, 6.2% agree and 0.5% disagreed. On the average, the respondents indicated that establishing new values based on institutional needs is high with a mean of 3.39. Results also showed that 47.4% of the respondents strongly agree that abandon outdated/routines 44.3% agree and 8.25 disagree. On the average, the respondents indicated that abandon outdated beliefs/routines is high with a mean of 3.39. The results showed that 38.1% of the respondents strongly agree that training On new work procedures, 53.6% agree and 8.2% disagree. On the average, the respondents indicated that training on new work procedures is high with a mean of 3.30 and organizational learning has a grand mean of 3.37.

The results aver that the grand mean for innovation drivers is 3.39 and based on the decision scale, suggests that the respondents agree with the statement representing innovation drivers are on the moderately high scale. This implies that the level of innovation drivers of administrative staff of tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria is relatively high and there exists opportunities for management to continue providing an enabling environment that allows for attaining higher level of innovation drivers.

Summary of regression analysis for the influence of innovation drivers on job performance of administrative staff of tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria

Model		F(df)	Anova Sig
R	0.669		
R Square	0.448	51.298 (3,190)	0.000
Adjusted R Square	0.439		
Coefficients	Unstandardized Coefficients	T	Sig
(Constant)	1.423	8.667	.000

Innovation culture	.171	4.009	.000
Management Competency	.232	4.513	.000
Organisational learning	.194	4.286	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), Innovation culture, Management Competency, Organizational learning

Source: Field Survey Results 2023

From the results, innovation drivers have strong positive and statistically significant relationship with the job performance of administrative staff of tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria ($R = 0.669$, $p < 0.05$). The coefficient of determination (Adj. R^2) of 0.439 shows that innovation drivers predict 43.9% of the changes in job performance of administrative staff, while the remaining 56.1% changes in job performance of administrative staff is attributable to other external factors other than those examined in this study. From the table the results of ANOVA (overall model significance) of regression test revealed that innovation drivers have a significant influence on job performance of administrative staff of tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria. This can be explained by the F-value (51.298) and low p-value (0.000) which is statistically significant at 95% confidence interval. Hence, the result posited that innovation drivers found in tertiary institutions in Edo State significantly influenced their administrative staff job performance.

Furthermore, the results of regression coefficients revealed that a positive and statistically significant relative influence was reported for all the innovation drivers considered. Specifically, the results reveal that at 95% confidence level, Innovation culture, ($\beta = 0.171$, $p = 0.000$, $t = 4.009$), Management Competency ($\beta = 0.232$, $p = 0.000$, $t = 4.513$), and Organizational learning ($\beta = 0.194$, $p = 0.000$, $t = 4.286$) of administrative staff of tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria were statistically significant as the p-values were less than 0.05 and the t-values greater than 1.96.

Also, looking at the results of regression coefficients, position that at 95% confidence level, a unit change in innovation culture will lead to a 0.171 increase in the job performance of administrative staff of tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria, given that all other factors are held constant. Similarly, a unit change in Management Competency will lead to a 0.232 increase in the job performance of administrative staff of tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria, given that all other factors are held constant. Lastly, the result also shows that a unit change in Organizational learning will lead to a 0.194 increase in the job performance of administrative staff of tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria, given that all other factors are held constant. Of all the innovation drivers examined, Management Competency has the highest relative effect on job performance (Beta=0.209) followed by organisational learning () and in third place is innovation culture (). It is important to stress that all the measures of innovation drivers had positive and significant relative influence on job performance of administrative staff of tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria. Given this result (Adj. $R^2 = 0.439$, $F(3,190) = 51.298$, $p = 0.000$), this study rejects the null hypothesis one (H_01) which states that innovation drivers will have no significant influence on the job performance of administrative staff of tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

It was found that administrative employees at tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria, are highly influenced by innovation drivers, supporting the first premise. The results of the first null hypothesis are consistent with those of other empirical investigations. One study that looked at the connection between innovation culture and productivity in the workplace was conducted in the Nigerian banking industry (Binder, Lancaster, Tobey, Jittrapirom & Yamagata 2019). The innovation culture dimensions used in this study were leadership styles, employee training, workflow, and employee dedication. Primary data was analysed using a questionnaire used in a field survey. The study's sample size was 392, and it was comprised of workers from the following Nigerian financial institutions: First Bank, Access Bank, Zenith Bank, Fidelity Bank, First City Monument Bank, United Bank for Africa, Diamond Bank, and Guaranty Trust Bank, Nigeria. Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) was utilised to estimate the framework's model parameters. SPSS 22.0 was used to perform both descriptive and inferential analyses on the collected data. The research showed that the banking industry in Nigeria has a strong culture of innovation. Employee performance improved across the board when innovation culture was emphasised. Therefore, the study suggested that businesses implement a culture of innovation to boost productivity.

A researcher looked at how much of an effect innovation culture has on workers' productivity. Examining the relationship between software companies in Pakistan and their employees' levels of innovation culture and productivity (Neilson, 2015). The methodology used in this study is a survey. This research made use of both primary and secondary sources. Questionnaires and both formal and informal interviews were used to collect primary data. Variables in this analysis include customer service, employee participation, incentive system, innovation & risk-taking, and communication system. Due to the small sample size (110), statistical methods such as correlation and regression analysis were employed. The findings as a whole show that a culture of innovation greatly benefits employee productivity in a few select Pakistani software companies. The contribution of employees is crucial to the success of any business. The need for research on the cultural influences on software workers in Pakistan has long been recognised, and this study helps to fill that need. A study was done on the "Effect of Innovation Culture on Employee Performance in Non-Governmental Organisations in Kenya"(Alolayyan, Al-Rwaidan, Hamadneh, Ahmad, Alhamad, Al-Hawary & Alshurideh 2022). This study used a descriptive survey approach to gather information from a specific group of people—World Vision Kenya's staff—via questionnaires to draw conclusions on how organisational innovation culture affects worker productivity. World Vision Kenya has a total of 960 employees, and a representative sample size of 484 was drawn from this group. Quantitative and qualitative methods, including SPSS (a statistical tool for social scientists), were used to examine the data. The research found that an organization's success is significantly affected by its culture of innovation since it determines the company's ideology, work environment, performance goals, and stability. World Vision Kenya is home to a diverse group of people who bring together elements of competitive, entrepreneurial, bureaucratic, and consensus-based cultures. Employees would rather work in an integrated culture than one that values consensus and entrepreneurship or competition and entrepreneurship. This is because workers nowadays choose an office setting that encourages them to use their imagination and creativity while also fostering team spirit and freedom from micromanagement.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The research concluded that digital innovation driver influences Job Performance of Administrative Staff in Tertiary Institutions, Edo State, Nigeria. Accordingly, data gathered from the administrative staff in administrative department in the investigated Institutions revealed that, there is need to enhance employee performance which is critical because it is key to better academic activities that would increase staff productivity, retains academics and eventually attain overall academic success. Innovation Drivers influence administrative staff performance in order to achieve the institutions' set out objectives. Innovation Drivers made the administrative staff to deliver better performance which eventually results in improved organizational success among these staff in tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria.

Based on the findings in this study, the following recommendations were made: The management of the tertiary institutions in Edo State, Nigeria should consistently improve on innovations among administrative staff such as innovation culture, management competency, and organizational learning to enhance the performance of administrative staff in the institutions. Given that innovation drivers influence the job performance of administrative staff in tertiary institutions in Edo State, managements of the tertiary institutions should provide necessary resources that will continue to advance their competence, improve learning and provide an environment driven by a culture of innovation.

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